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Distributive foundations of contract law

A reappraisal

José Antonio Sánchez Rubín

1 Introduction

- 1 Among the contemporary debates regarding private law, the theorization of the moral foundations of contract law has been nothing but profound. Different positions have been categorized under several labels, such as the fundamental distinction between deontological (e.g., will, autonomy-based, and transfer theories) and consequentialist conceptions (e.g., those rooted in law and economics methodology and distributive justice considerations). Yet, most of these characterizations cannot adequately explain and justify contract rules,¹ either because they cannot grasp all the relevant features of contemporary voluntary transactions, or they irremediably lose sight of the core content of contractual rules.
- 2 In the face of this panorama, an early admonition must be issued. When it comes to theoretical endeavours regarding legal practices, Coleman warns us, a significant source of disagreement arises from methodological decisions induced by the favouritism towards a particular moral principle (or, as the author calls it, a “foundational view”).² For instance, while a common law lawyer could favour a promissory account of contract law,³ a continental jurist would emphasize the role of the parties’ wills.⁴ Insofar as some contractarians are keen to reject public intervention in private exchanges—given the liberal constraint of neutrality—others are open to considering this set of rules as tools to achieve valuable social goals.⁵ While deontological scholars focus on the formal correction of the bargain process and consequentialist theorists explain the institution in terms of its ability to produce efficient states of affairs,⁶ progressive thinkers demand positive actions from the State whenever the dignity of the parties requires it,⁷ and so forth.

- 3 Of course, Coleman’s claim should not deter scholars from attempting to theorize contract law. Thus, my purpose is to offer an alternative perspective that may help address some of these shortcomings beyond the peculiarities found in doctrinal debates. To this end, I will offer a novel philosophical perspective focused on the social functions performed by contract law, suggesting an interpretation of its rules in light of the egalitarian ideal according to which moral agents can only be liable for their own deeds.
- 4 To this end, I will begin by presenting a morally uncompromised description of the main features of contract law, postulating that its rules establish an institutional form for the practice of voluntary exchanges. The outcome will be a functional description of contract law, i.e., a depiction focused on the alleged positive effects of its rules on the relevant social system. Such a description can be summarized as follows: two of the functions of contract law are to stabilize voluntary exchanges and to neutralize misfortunes relevant to the contractual practice. This means that contracts facilitate cooperative endeavours —among which voluntary transactions of goods and services are a paradigmatic expression— and that they provide legal mechanisms to offset the effects of unexpected contingencies.
- 5 Next, I will provide a philosophical account of how such an institution might be justifiable in the broader context of democratic liberal societies. In this regard, I take the methodological assumption that the political acceptability of social institutions can be morally assessed in instrumental terms by reference to the functions they achieve. Subsequently, I discuss the evaluative yield of two moral ideals for a distributive interpretation of contract law: significant autonomy, on the one hand, and the egalitarian principle of offsetting morally arbitrary factors from determining people’s shares of welfare or resources, on the other.
- 6 In principle, it might be thought that the political morality ideal of significant autonomy is a suitable basis for having an institution that enforces voluntary exchanges insofar as contract law works. Contracts work, using Razian terminology, as instruments that enhance personal autonomy by increasing the valuable alternatives from which people can choose in their pursuit of a worthwhile life.⁸ As Kimel puts it, parties can address some of the tasks necessary to fulfil and achieve their life plans by cooperating with others.⁹
- 7 However, this proposal faces several shortcomings in providing a basis for a public morality of contract law. Briefly, Raz’s liberal project cannot account for the influence of luck in human action, a deficiency that should, in logical terms, extend to any contract conception grounded on this interpretation of institutional phenomena. In contrast, I will present an alternative conception that responds to the egalitarian intuition that excludes morally arbitrary causes from determining interpersonal levels of welfare or resources.

2 A functional description of contracts

- 8 As announced, the first step in coming to a solution is to present a *minimal* characterization of the law of contracts. This can be attained by focusing on the main features observed in current legal practice and providing a secular, non-moral, or morally neutral description of what contract law *actually does*.

- 9 Like currency, punishment, or even family, law is a social institution, whereas contracts are, like promises, an institutional form of the voluntary exchange of goods and services.¹⁰ Following Buckley, the characterization of contract law as a social institution rests on the implicit assumption that a pre-established convention is required to attribute a specific meaning to the actions performed under its dominion.¹¹ Following Searle's teachings, these conventions come together into constitutive rules that enable us to assess whether an exchange corresponds to an institutional expression of a contract, insofar as its parties act in accordance with a previously defined behaviour.¹² While intuitive, one might enquire into questions such as, what is implied by the statement 'X counts as Y in context C'¹³ when applied to contract law? And, when does a voluntary exchange count as a contract in contemporary private law systems?
- 10 These questions are partly ontological and partly functional. Ontologically, contract law, like its 'relative' promises, is an existing institutional form that orders human transactions. Both institutions share, as a salient feature, the condition of voluntariness underlying the acts of self-imposing obligations favouring either the creditor or the promisee. This commonality favours the assimilation of a single moral foundation for the compulsory effect of the corresponding obligations. As Fried suggested, if contracts are legally binding, it is because there is a moral obligation to keep one's promises.¹⁴
- 11 However, I am not concerned with inquiring into the philosophical foundations of contract law, since a morally uncompromised depiction of contract law is necessary to avoid the imminent peril of a *petitio principii* fallacy. In contrast to scholars like Fried, I will argue that, from the sociological standpoint, the institutional nature of contract allows us to focus on its functions. To this end, it should be first noted that a paradigmatic feature of contracts is the prerogative conceded to one party, who we call the creditor, to lean on the public enforcement of her *in personam* right against the other party, the debtor.¹⁵ The State comes into play in exchange relations by lending its coercive powers against the debtor, provided that both parties have *acted* in a predetermined manner.
- 12 To illustrate this, let us consider two scenarios: Scenario 1 (S1) and Scenario 2 (S2). On the one hand, in the pre-institutional state S1, Johnny and June regularly exchange the excess of the products that they collect daily. On the other hand, in the institutional scenario S2, they exchange their goods following a set of preexisting rules enacted either by convention or by a sovereign power. Such rules prescribe, among other matters, the use of currency in private transactions (R1), the compulsory effect of the reciprocally assumed obligations (R2), and mandate the use of a particular solemnity to express their conformity with the agreement, like shaking hands accompanied by a ceremonial phrase ('Deal!') (R3). This *legal* background transforms the brute fact of exchanging, which is represented in S1, into a contract within the institutional setting of S2.
- 13 To provide a complete account of the contemporary practice of contract law, this rudimentary depiction requires a detailed explanation of R3. As specified in S2, parties enter a contract by acting in a certain way, such as following certain ritualistic forms. These formalities are historically contingent. We might think of archaic legal systems where the institutionally relevant act rested on allegories and symbolisms, like a little tap on the traded good or on an object that represented it to manifest the agreement, such as striking a scale with a piece of bronze while holding the acquired thing. In

contemporary contracting systems, the role of R3 generally corresponds to the rules governing the agreement in English law, and *consentement* in the French legal family.¹⁶

- 14 From a theoretical standpoint, Barnett interprets consent as a rule that fulfils an informative function.¹⁷ This is to say that, as a condition for validly transferring legal rights, the contracting parties must reciprocally manifest their consent “in a manner that provides a criterion of enforcement”.¹⁸ Through consent, contract law not only identifies when a contractual obligation is coercible but also determines whose performance can be demanded. In this regard, consent can be considered a token (and R3 its constitutive rule), which turns a brute exchange into an institutional one. Consequently, contractual obligations can be compulsorily coerced as both debtor and creditor have consented to bend to this pre-established legal effect.
- 15 To complete the outline of the role of consensual contractual obligations, let me reflect on the conceptual differences between them and their opposite institutional forms for resource transference: tort law. A historical insight can serve this explanatory task, given the prevalence of the Gayan-Justinian systematization of private law obligations, namely, the Aristotelian distinction between voluntary and nonvoluntary transactions¹⁹ in Classical Roman Law, the *summa divisio* of obligations settled on the distinction between those arising from contracts, on the one hand, and those arising from delicts, on the other.²⁰ Since then, it has been broadly assumed that contracts rest on voluntariness, meaning that the parties to a contract acted *understanding* that they were creating obligations.²¹ Under tort law, however, the causal explanation to the relevant obligations rest on an involuntary basis,²² since the wrongdoer did not intend to be legally bound to the victim of her unlawful act. In classical contract theory terms, this explains the dogmatic consensus marking *voluntariness* as a conceptual feature of contracts and the role of consent as the legal explanation for its binding effect.²³ As the nineteenth-century doctrine made clear, voluntariness explained the enforceability of private agreements, which rested on their characterization as genuine expressions of the parties’ wills.²⁴
- 16 According to the institutional approach presented here, the voluntariness condition is required for the legal effect of contracts (which, in turn, is the mandatory nature of their obligations as R2 prescribes) to be obtained. In this sense, through R3, consent refers to the specific action recognized by contract law to make these obligations mandatory for whoever enters into such agreements. As Barnett puts it, “Courts should presumptively enforce private commitments when there exists a manifested intention to create a legal relation”.²⁵
- 17 This analysis illustrates the role of consent as a rule that attributes the effect of making a specific action coercible in institutional exchanges. For instance, in S1, Johnny or June can always behave strategically, considering the convenience of complying or deserting on a case-by-case basis. On the contrary, in S2, as any jurist would agree, the performance of the contract is no longer optional. The parties to a contract assume a reciprocal duty to comply, and most importantly, for reasons that I will explain further below, they can also *count on it*.²⁶
- 18 As can be anticipated, the assumption of an institutional approach to depicting contract law also allows us to explain this institution by referring to its social effects. Conceptually different from purposes, functions are defined as the favourable effects that institutions produce on the pertinent social system.²⁷ Following this assumption, I

argue below that the social virtues of contract law consist in its capacity to cope with the problems arising from the background of uncertainty intrinsic to human affairs.²⁸

- 19 Following the law and economics literature, contract law can be thought of as a mechanism through which its parties allocate benefits and losses (ostensibly of a pecuniary nature) arising from their cooperation, including the effects of future risks.²⁹ In this sense, contracts can be described as risk prevention arrangements, as the parties can create schemes that reduce or prevent possible adverse outcomes, e.g., in expert-non-expert relations, or to apportion costs to those in a better position to absorb them, as is the paradigmatic purpose of insurance contracts. Consider, for instance, a contractual scheme designed by Montgomery and Richard to manage future risks, where the former is a risk-averse person and the latter is risk-prone. Through their contract, Montgomery acquires from Richard the necessary materials to build a shelter for natural disasters. In Montgomery's deliberative process, his risk averseness defeats any other consideration, even the economic efficiency of this particular transaction. In contrast, in the face of the same risk, Richard's preferences favour alternative uses for the expected remuneration. While living in a hurricane zone, Montgomery will most likely acquire extra supplies (say, bottled water or canned food) from Richard, even at a high price, regardless of how remote the probability of such a natural disaster is. Nevertheless, both parties will consider their agreement a good deal: Montgomery will reinforce his feeling of safety, and, in return, Richard will satisfy some hedonistic desire by spending the extra money on an exotic vacation.
- 20 Nevertheless, foresight exercises do not cover all possible risks. This feature of human agency is, properly, a problem of epistemic uncertainty. First, by entering a transaction, each party is *betting* on compliance with their agreement. However, in terms of our hypothetical case, we can ask how Montgomery can trust Richard, given that, in his eyes, he has much more to lose due to the latter's reckless nature? Second, it is worth noting that in institutionalized contract scenarios, the future contingencies effectively considered by the parties are not the only relevant ones. Since omniscience is not a feature of the human decision-making process, benefits and losses arising from unknown circumstances at the time of execution are real and, consequently, should also matter.
- 21 In the described context, contract law plays two complementary functions in contemporary systems. Its most prominent function is to make voluntary exchanges plausible, given that whoever submits to its rules can be forced to keep their word. In this regard, it can be said that contracts stabilize voluntary exchanges by assigning incentives and disincentives to the contracting parties, so that they can count on the opposing party's reliability, *even if they are not eager to comply*.³⁰ Here, the description that contracts correspond to a scheme of local cooperation for mutual advantage works on a rational choice paradigm of contractual parties as utility maximisers. In this sense, contracts are to be enforced insofar as they can be justified as a matter of individual rationality. But, one might ask, what does this assertion mean?
- 22 By definition, rational agents seek to maximize their utility.³¹ Consequently, on this view, human cooperation is only rationally justifiable if the collaborative result (i.e., compliance) improves its opposite result (i.e., breach), considering the costs of the safeguards that parties must take and the resulting benefit-loss calculus.³² But, as part of their own decision, agents would also need to know whether the other party will be as eager as they are to comply with their pledged word. This problem can be explained

in terms of the prisoner's dilemma, a theoretical exercise designed to demonstrate that the optimal outcome for each player does not necessarily coincide with the optimal outcome in collective terms, given the co-dependency of each player's decisions.³³ As Coleman explains, parties will comply to the extent that an external arrangement allows the expected utility from cooperation to supersede the expected utility from defection, or $U_i \geq D_i$.³⁴

- 23 In this regard, contract remedies can be described as institutional corrections to solve the prisoner's dilemma. By making private arrangements coercible, contract law fulfils the function of stabilizing voluntary exchanges, or the *stabilizing function*.³⁵ This means that contract law addresses this particular cooperation problem by setting incentives in a way that allows for cooperation by making compliance justifiable in terms of individual rationality. It is through remedies such as expectation damages, specific performance, or even termination that the non-cooperative strategy no longer dominates its opposite by turning the rational calculus $U_i \leq D_i$ into $U_i \geq D_i$.
- 24 In his highly detailed explanation of the effects produced by contract law, Coleman distinguishes three rationality principles involved in three phases of contractual relations: the pre-phase, the negotiation phase, and the post-phase. In the pre-phase, parties that are not legally bound decide whether to execute a contract with each other. Here, the rational dilemma refers to entering a contract with the counterparty. Specifically, following Coleman's analysis, this is a cooperation rationality problem where the parties apply the $U_i \geq D_i$ algorithm to deliberate between the cooperation and non-cooperation alternatives. Here, the main issue consists of information problems involving market failures, which, from a legal point of view, are the subject matter of information disclosures.
- 25 In the negotiation phase, parties bargain over the contract's content, which, as described earlier, is a question of how future risks will be contractually distributed. In addition to the information problems, the issue of opportunism reappears. As Coleman proposes, in this phase, the collaborative strategy will only dominate the non-cooperative alternative to the extent that the parties concede, thereby obtaining a lower than expected utility.
- 26 However, strategic behaviour is not the only peril that can lead to contract failure. During the performance of contract obligations, unexpected circumstances may also arise, some of which could have a sufficiently significant magnitude to distort the $U_i \geq D_i$ calculus by increasing the performance costs or even rendering it impossible to comply with the promised benefits. If $U_i \geq D_i$ turns into $U_i \leq D_i$, the rationality condition for cooperation fails. However, from a legal perspective, the injured party can still be legally compelled to fulfil their obligations, even if this results in a severe economic loss. This is possible since contract law plays the accessory function of endorsing the stabilizing function before the occurrence of uncontrollable contingencies for its parties. This particular effect, created by contract law, has been referred to as the function of neutralizing contractual misfortunes, or just the *neutralizing function*.³⁶
- 27 The neutralizing function encompasses various rules, from those that govern the force majeure and act of God hypothesis to those that alleviate the rigor of the contracted obligations, such as the severe hardship doctrine. In this regard, contract law works as a mechanism that allows parties to stipulate, in a coercible manner, *ad hoc* rules for future contingencies. However, it has been argued that contract law not only

safeguards parties against specified circumstances but also enacts rules dealing with events that might arise from unforeseen and uncontrolled situations that can occur during the execution of contractual obligations.³⁷ Relating to what is known as contractual liability,³⁸ the old Roman aphorism *impossibile nulla obligatio est* (which can be roughly translated as ‘the impossible is no legal obligation’) generically refers to the situations in which a contract can be annulled whenever its ‘object’ —i.e., what is contractually owed— is physically or legally impossible (e.g., the sale of an inexistent good such as hippocentaurs or the agreement to sell the *Campus Martius*).³⁹ In English contract law, it has been explained that while the classical attitude was unsympathetic towards exoneration based on the initial impossibility, contemporarily this ruling is recognized as part of the doctrine of frustration.⁴⁰ In the continental tradition, both the French (Articles 1351) and Chilean civil codes (Article 1682) offer a similar solution by stipulating the annullability of such contracts.

- 28 The impossibility can also arise from superseding events, which is the natural territory of the rules of *cas fortuit* and *force majeure*. While English contract law contains the doctrine of frustration, the French Civil Code contains default rules that order automatic termination as of the date the contract was frustrated,⁴¹ and the release of the debtor when she proves that the loss of the owed thing would also have occurred if the obligation had been performed (Article 1351-1). With certain peculiarities, Chilean sales contract law adopts a similar solution, rendering this supervenient circumstance as a ground to terminate the vendor’s obligations. In contrast with the rule from its French precedent, the buyer can still be coerced into fulfilling her obligation to pay (Articles 1550 and 1567 7° of the Chilean Civil Code).⁴²
- 29 It should be noted that the materialization of unforeseen risks does not necessarily terminate contractual obligations. If the impossibility is not absolute, the difficulties might also be considered to mitigate liability due to less decisive circumstances, such as the severe hardship hypothesis,⁴³ and even restrict the scope of recoverable losses by excluding compensation for remote damages. In this last regard, the rule enacted in *Hadley v Baxendale* orders the rejection of compensation for remote damages based on the assertion that the defendant could not have foreseen them at the time the contract concluded, considering the usual course of things or what the parties could have reasonably contemplated as probable.⁴⁴ Similarly, in both the French and Chilean Civil Codes (Articles 1231-3 and 1550, respectively), compensable damages are limited to the losses arising from direct and foreseeable consequences of the breach, at least if the debtor did not intentionally cause the breach (due to *fraude* or *dolo*).
- 30 Let me recapitulate the argument so far. Through its functions, contract law enables consenting parties to prevent, distribute, or transfer risks. In this conceptual scheme, both functions coordinate to address potential contractual failures arising from unexpected circumstances, given the context of epistemic uncertainty within which human affairs take place. Whereas the stabilizing function operates against the ignorance of what the other party might do or whether she will comply, the neutralizing function faces uncertainty regarding circumstances external to the particular contract relation.

3 Razian interpretations of contract law

- 31 With the functional depiction of contracts, the descriptive basis has been set to assess the normative task of identifying the moral principles that underlie that particular legal practice, presenting it —as Dworkin would say— in its best light. The purpose of this section, then, is to inquire into the justificatory performance of two philosophical principles of public morality that, in my opinion, are plausible candidates to properly comprehend the practice of institutional voluntary agreements. I am referring, on the one hand, to the significant autonomy ideal defended by Raz, and on the other, to the liberal egalitarian ideal, according to which morally arbitrary circumstances should not influence people's welfare or resources, as posed by authors like Rawls and Dworkin.
- 32 In *The Morality of Freedom*, Raz justifies political authority through the ideal of political freedom. To this end, he introduces the notion of significant autonomy, which contrasts with the classical negative conception of freedom, which corresponds to the mere absence of coercion induced by others. Concerning this positive conception of liberty, Kimel, using Berlin's words,⁴⁵ has argued in favour of a notion that also emphasizes the possibility of being one's own master, or being partly the author of one's own life.⁴⁶ In a liberal social scheme compatible with a pluralistic conception of the good, the institutions are to be ordered in a way that secures freedom not only from third-party coercion but also from constraints arising from circumstances, as their political legitimacy rests in their capacity to allow people to pursue their autonomously defined life plans freely.⁴⁷
- 33 Notedly, significant autonomy implies a conception of freedom that requires each individual to have a bundle of morally acceptable options. Accordingly, people should be able to choose how to lead their own lives,⁴⁸ since it is an ideal of free and conscious self-creation.⁴⁹ Nevertheless, as Raz warns, individual well-being is not necessarily restricted to the agents' capacity for free or deliberate choice. For instance, family relations can also be considered paradigmatic expressions of individual well-being since they are usually voluntarily embraced, even though they are not necessarily freely chosen. Raz's point is eminently conceptual: well-being is associated with the *willing* embracement of one's life, which is not limited to the genuine choices of agents.⁵⁰ In sum, significant autonomy refers to the possibility of leading a valuable life, in such a way that it results from the exercise of autonomous agents' capacities to actively shape their lives, and determine their course, i.e., free from coercion. This is to say that this conception of autonomy is the property of autonomous agents being, at least partially, authors of their own lives.⁵¹
- 34 Consistently, the commitment to the liberal project of promoting significant autonomy requires a conception of political morality much more robust than the simple absence of coercion. Indeed, the broader concept of coercion translates into a strong notion of autonomy, as it encompasses not only freedom from the interference of others (the classical content of negative freedom) but also extends to non-coercive interferences, such as those that affect the agent's personal needs and natural conditions. In this regard, the significant autonomy ideal demands that liberal societies guarantee individuals the ability to rationally choose between valuable alternatives according to their particular conceptions of the good. On its behalf, social institutions are to be arranged under the ideal of significant autonomy, which in turn requires that they should not necessarily be neutral in relation to people's life plans. As Raz argued,

neutrality is to be asserted regarding conceptions of good, but not about the life prospects of individuals.⁵²

- 35 In its application to the moral foundation of contract law, significant autonomy might be suggested as a suitable moral ideal to justify the existence of an institution that enforces voluntary exchanges, since, again using Raz's phrasing, contracts can be considered instruments that increase the valuable alternatives among which people must choose. By cooperating with others, parties can address some of the tasks necessary to pursue their goals in accordance with their conception of the good.⁵³ Returning to our hypothetical case, Montgomery's life plan is tied to being—or feeling—safe from tragedies. At the same time, Richard does not require such preventive measures because he prefers to invest his time and resources in other things. But, despite their differences, both plans are feasible thanks to contract law, as each party requires the cooperation of the other to achieve self-realization.
- 36 Conceding, for the sake of the argument, that these considerations might ground the stabilization function of contract law, it should be asked if they can have a bearing on the moral foundation of its complementary function of neutralizing contractual misfortunes. At first glance, it might seem that the rules carrying out the neutralizing function of the contract are, essentially, distributive-based since they coercively reallocate the losses suffered by the non-faulty party to either her counterpart or the relevant community. However, it should also be noted that such allocations must comply with a specific normative or moral criterion that amends the patrimonial effects arising from unforeseeable or insurmountable circumstances. For the primary function of *stabilizing*—arguably the main interest of contract theorists—the appeal of Raz's notion of autonomy is quite clear. While authors like Fried argue that the binding effect of contracts is required to respect the personal rights and exercise of autonomy carried out by the contracting parties,⁵⁴ others, such as Kronman, argue that its foundation lies in its capability to set the proper incentives to produce acceptable resource allocation.⁵⁵ But, then again, since the creditor can rely on the debtor's cooperative behaviour, it can be argued that contracts facilitate the pursuit of an agent's ends by reducing the uncertainties surrounding private agreements and solving rationality problems. Therefore, contracts promote (significant) autonomy by facilitating the pursuit of people's life plans and making collaborative enterprises plausible. As Kimel's autonomy promotion conception suggests,⁵⁶ the value of contracts resides in their function of personal detachment, which assures compliance by emancipating the plausibility of the agreement from preexisting or future personal relations between the parties.⁵⁷
- 37 Additionally, Razian interpretations may allow us to explore further implications for the justificatory endeavour of contract law. Particularly, I think of their potential contribution to settling the adjoining controversy regarding the adscription of contracts to distributive justice goals. While commonly resisted, distributive justice accounts of contract law remain a main topic within the legal discussion.⁵⁸
- 38 Kronman canonically summarized the core of the distributive justice matter in contract law. He asserted that what is at stake in distributive interpretations of contracts is a public morality commitment according to which “those responsible for choosing or designing rules of contract law—courts and legislatures—should do so with an eye to their distributional effects in a self-conscious effort to achieve a fair division of wealth

among the members of society”.⁵⁹ I shall refer to this argument as the distributive query.

- 39 For the sake of the argument, assume that contract law is actually designed for substantial equality purposes. In that case, following Kimel, it might be argued that significant autonomy allows us to reassess the neutral standpoint traditionally attributed to the institutional role of contract law—and, foremost, private law itself—in securing the conditions for self-realization. Therefore, a *progressive* private law is necessary in the broad terms of social justice beyond the particular case presented before the judicial system. A judge is no longer required to settle the private dispute before considering the litigants’ *in personam* rights; she must also produce a rule aligned with the public *ethos* that justifies the social system. This is not due to an internal moral basis within private law relationships, like deontological theorists tend to insist, but because the legitimacy of public powers that enact these rules requires such political commitment.
- 40 Still, this argument requires further elaboration. Traditional contract theories, deontological in character, such as Fried’s autonomy account or Benson’s transference theory, rest on the Kantian idea of innate freedom, i.e., “independence from being constrained by another’s choice”.⁶⁰ If these institutional agreements are to be justiciable, it is because such an effect is required to respect the parties’ rights, freedoms, or autonomy, leaving no room for a public deliberation according to a particular social justice value. For instance, Benson identifies breach of contract as an unlawful interference by the defendant in the plaintiff’s right to possess and enjoy under the terms of the convention, in the same way as the damage corresponds to the loss of that right, given the transactional nature of contracts.⁶¹
- 41 At first glance, it seems correct to assert that, through cooperation, people can pursue their life goals with less effort and costs. Since they can count on the other party to keep their promise, due to the stabilizing function of contracts, pursuing their life plans is more attainable than trying to achieve them on their own. Returning to Montgomery and Richard’s example, Montgomery can prevent potential losses involving hunger or worse. At the same time, Richard can use the money to fulfil his dream of participating in the ‘running of the bulls’ activity in the Festival of San Fermín. Their contract made it at least partially possible for both parties to satisfy their own conception of the good, given the specific material conditions within which their lives take place.
- 42 But there is more. In current legal practice, contract law is not limited to ensuring the integrity of the consent expressed by the parties. Normatively speaking, by introducing new rules and legal statutes as a consequence of social progress and productive transformations, contract law surpasses the eminently formalist approach of traditional contract jurisprudence. A clear manifestation of significant autonomy’s philosophical influence on the primary function of contract law can be found in rules such as unilateral information duties, since they not only address the rationality issues that threaten human cooperation but also do so in *distributively relevant* human activities. Consider, for instance, commercial relations characterized by severe asymmetries in negotiating, and economic capacities, such as contracts with consumers,⁶² or where the satisfaction of basic human necessities and personal integrity are at stake, such as in the food industry,⁶³ financial services,⁶⁴ healthcare services,⁶⁵ and medical products.⁶⁶

- 43 Additionally, it might be argued that significant autonomy can be summoned to justify specific contract law rules with progressive vocation. Consider, for instance, the unconscionability doctrine from United States *common law*. In cases of what Kimel calls morally repugnant undertakings,⁶⁷ unconscionability is a doctrine that allows courts to refuse the enforcement of heavily exploitative or unfair contracts,⁶⁸ such as usurious loan rates or liability disclaims of warranties and consequential damages in sale agreements.⁶⁹ Similar conclusions can be drawn regarding relatively novel statutes prohibiting discrimination against protected classes of individuals, the enactment of pre-contractual information duties, and the prohibition of unfair commercial practices in English consumer law.⁷⁰
- 44 Furthermore, the Razian approach may approve progressive goals that many deontological theorists would probably disagree with. For instance, his autonomy ideal may justify the transplantation of the contractual institution to areas far beyond the scope of private law. Allow me to elaborate on this topic. By *lending* the bilateral structure of correlative rights and duties to typically asymmetrical relations, contract rules contribute to achieving valuable social goals (say, equality) since they provide a legal form that, arguably, instantiates the substantive feature of normative equivalency between what parties owe to each other. In labour law, for instance, the use of the contractual institution evinces the correlation between the ordered work and the wage (whatever the quantity may be) that is paid in return. In the field of hazardous activities, like passenger transport or medicine, by ‘contractualizing’ services massively offered to laypersons, lawmakers implement binding security *personal* obligations that can be coerced against the offeror who has control of the activity and is consequently in a better position to mitigate eventual risks or perils to their provision. This sort of rule is an instantiation of the significant autonomy ideal, as it makes certain levels of security mandatory for the offeror, allowing non-experts to pursue activities that they would otherwise be unable to conduct.
- 45 So far, so good: significant autonomy provides a strong argument in favour of the contracts' primary function. Yet, as I argued earlier, a satisfactory account of contract law requires that the moral ideal selected as a basis for contract law, whatever it might be, should also demonstrate a reasonable justificatory performance of the neutralizing function that this institution produces. If this is not attained, then the contract law justificatory enterprise is far from over. The evaluation of the Razian inspiration for contract theories will be the goal of the following section.

4 Towards an egalitarian theory of contracts

- 46 From a public morality perspective, significant autonomy is about making people authors of their lives, meaning that in a liberal society its institutions are to be ordered towards that end. However, this ideal is not committed to the actual success in achieving those autonomously defined goals, since its directives only extend to the moral appropriateness of the options the agents must choose to pursue such ends. Raz was quite explicit on this.⁷¹ Significant autonomy's justificatory job ends, so to speak, by setting up an institutional context that allows citizens to rationally choose between a set of valuable options to conduct their life prospects.⁷² Does this mean that people actually *deserve* all of the achievements and failures attained in their lifetime?

- 47 To shed light on this issue, let me recall a well-known example in the moral luck literature presented by Williams.⁷³ Gauguin was a painter whose artistic project included living the lifestyle of a *poète maudit*, an accursed poet. However, as moral luck philosophers stress, his destiny could not be exclusively attributed to his decisions, given the numerous external events that also played a part in shaping his life's outcome. Biographical accidents like his parents left-wing political activity, his childhood in Peru, or that he presumably suffered from a disease that, at that time had no treatment, may have influenced his emotional development, artistic opportunity accessibility, keenness for eccentric tastes, and even his (nowadays preventable) low-key death. How much of his artistic attainment can be attributed to him? Can he be made responsible for his posthumous fame? Can we, with no shade of doubt, agree with Kantians and explain his fate exclusively in terms of his moral agency?
- 48 While Gauguin's fateful life would not pose a problem for the liberal project that Raz's ideal of autonomy embodies, for moral luck philosophers his case illustrates the influence of luck in people's lives and demands, on their view, to attribute a role in our moral judgments. This results in the core stipulation according to which the reproach or praise of a specific action is, to some degree, determined by the occurrence of an event beyond the agent's control. In his canonical formulation of moral luck, Nagel stated that "where a significant aspect of what someone does depends on factors beyond his control, yet we continue to treat him in that respect as an object of moral judgment, it can be called moral luck".⁷⁴
- 49 To illustrate his point, Nagel provides the example of a reckless driver who kills an innocent pedestrian.⁷⁵ It seems that our moral intuitions are tinged in a way that the contempt towards James, a reckless driver who nevertheless arrives at work uneventfully, is not equivalent to our appreciation about Johnny, an inattentive driver who ran over a pedestrian on his way home. This observation holds even if, from a causal perspective, the fatality is not explained only by Johnny's absent-minded action but also by elements outside his control, say, the presence of the victim in that precise time and place. In some way, Johnny deserves a more severe appraisal than James even though both men act equivalently. To narrow the intuition down, we must acknowledge, alongside moral luck philosophers like Nagel, and luck egalitarians like Dworkin and Cohen, that some key features of our moral assessments come from concepts such as preference, choice, and control. Nelkin synthesized this opinion in the axiom of the 'control principle', which states that "we are morally assessable only to the extent that what we are assessed for depends on factors under our control".⁷⁶
- 50 If moral luck is taken seriously, we must accordingly ask if the effects of such contingencies in the success or failure of human endeavours should also play a role in the political appraisal of social institutions, including, of course, contract law. While I can agree with autonomy promotion conceptions of contract like Kimel's —given, among other reasons, the symmetry between his personal detachment function and my stabilizing function— this consensus should be extended with important reservations precisely because my critical contention arises from the need for social institutions to attend to circumstances that, while influencing the success of life projects, cannot be solely attributed to their authors. This criticism can be stated as follows: if the promotion of autonomy were a suitable goal to (instrumentally) justify the coercive nature of contracts, an additional normative criterion would be necessary to ground a further public intervention in favour of the contracting party suffering a misfortune.

- 51 The observed deficiency suggests an additional philosophical standpoint from which contract law can be comprehended. For the sake of concision, it should suffice to say that on a liberal interpretation of private law, the conceptual premises of egalitarianism are available.⁷⁷ By reading Rawls' influential account of liberalism, it could be stated that the central intuition behind liberal egalitarian thought excludes the incidence of morally arbitrary circumstances, such as accidents of natural endowment and the contingencies of social circumstance, in prospecting people's life plans.⁷⁸ In fact, according to his conception of liberalism, the principles of justice that govern the well-ordered society exclude such factors from the allocation of primary goods, i.e., the necessary means for "forming and rationally pursuing" any conception of the good.⁷⁹ This results in the proscription of the lottery behind natural endowments as a legitimate justificative reason for interpersonal inequalities. Hereinafter, I shall refer to such ideal as the *egalitarian principle*.
- 52 What implications might the egalitarian principle have for a liberal interpretation of private law and contract law? First and foremost, it demands solving the apparent tension between the rationale behind the traditional features of private law, such as the correlative rights and duties structure identified by Weinrib,⁸⁰ and the assertion that luck propitiates legal responsibility. To this end, the egalitarian principle suggests reconstructing the notion of consequential responsibility in light of a central claim, namely, discarding that private law subjects are liable as if they were holders, as nineteenth-century jurists assumed, of an unconditioned will and, consequently, that they can be liable only for states of affairs over which they had a certain degree of control.⁸¹
- 53 While an orthodox objector would contend that, being the neutralization of natural lottery belonging to the domain of distributive justice, the plausibility of this interpretation would be conceptually or morally inadmissible as a basis for the evaluation of private acquisitions. Furthermore, she may add that Rawls himself formulated the argument for this constraint.⁸² I believe that such contention, while coherent with traditional conceptions of private law, can be countered by proposing a revision of Rawls' arguments around the subjects of his principles of justice, namely, the institutions that comprise what he refers to as constituents of the basic structure of society. If I succeed, a Rawlsian argument favouring the use of private law rules to achieve distributive goals is likely plausible. This will be my next argument.
- 54 Arguably, the dominant position regarding contractual justice forbids both distributive and redistributive purposes for private law, since the basis for supporting the coercivity of the institutions governing private relations can only lie in respecting parties' rights. In line with theories that address private law in terms of the ideal of corrective or commutative justice,⁸³ contemporary political philosophy provides an additional reason against public intervention in private exchanges and the inclusion of distributive justice goals into their legal regime.⁸⁴ I am referring to the basic structure objection, which rests on the view that the public and private philosophical basis for justification lay in different moral principles.⁸⁵ Based on Rawls' theory of justice as fairness, the objection assumes that social justice is a virtue of social institutions since, as this author claims, the basic structure of society is the primary subject of social justice.⁸⁶ From this definition, it is derived that the scope of the Rawlsian principles of justice, including the 'distributive' difference principle, is constrained to "the way in which the major social institutions distribute fundamental rights and duties and

determine the division of advantages from social cooperation”,⁸⁷ this is to say, to the justification of the political constitution and other institutional arrangements like property and markets.⁸⁸

- 55 At first glance, the demarcation between distributively relevant social institutions and the rules governing private transactions seems clear, to the point where a division of labour between them seems necessary to preserve just social conditions.⁸⁹ While the social system preserves the background conditions of social justice through distributive and redistributive mechanisms such as taxes, private law allows its parties to freely pursue their ends within the framework provided by the basic structure.⁹⁰ As Cohen interprets the division of labour argument, the difference principle only applies “to the choice of institutions and not to the choices made within them”.⁹¹ In other words, social justice should be a property of private transactions but be situated in the institutional background, like the market system, upon which they occur. It is the justification of the latter, not the former, which should result from directly applying the principles of justice as fairness.⁹²
- 56 Against this interpretation, a Rawlsian perspective has retorted that private law may also rest on distributive considerations by reinterpreting the basic structure objection.⁹³ To this end, it is suggested that contracts are so relevant to each individual life project, as deontological theorists propose, that they also participate in that broader—and fundamental— institutional background. Furthermore, bearing in mind institutions that Rawls regarded as part of his basic structure, it follows that private law is not, *on an a priori* basis, absolutely excluded from his principles of justice. And, supporting the argument in favour of a social justice-oriented contract law, it also appears that it is intertwined with the rules governing markets and private property, since the former is the regime for acquiring goods. Then, attending to the functions and purposes of the institution, there should not be, on Rawls’ theoretical framework, any further conceptual reason to exclude contract law as the subject of distributive justice.⁹⁴
- 57 But now, if distributive justice is a plausible goal for contract law, it is necessary to show how it fulfils such a purpose and, mainly, in what way the egalitarian principle is implicit in its rules. To this end, and to provide a conceptual basis for distributive and redistributive individual claims, I will resort to the Dworkinian distinction between brute and option luck, where people can be entitled to a claim against the community under the luck egalitarianism theories.⁹⁵
- 58 In Dworkin’s conception of social justice as fair insurance, the distinction between brute and option luck specifies the tension between moral responsibility and luck. Since the egalitarian principle orders compensations for inequities in people’s resources, a normative criterion is necessary to identify which variations in their initial portion of resources are assigned through the hypothetical mechanism of an initial auction.⁹⁶ Dworkin’s answer is based on another hypothetical device, an open insurance market, which equally allows citizens to acquire insurance against contingencies in return for whatever portion of their original bundle of resources they deem fit. This specific exercise of a *preference* provides the basis for justification when a particular misfortune can give rise to a distributive claim within a specific political community.
- 59 To illustrate the implications of this conception of equality, consider the situation of two individuals with different lifestyles, Naylor and Don, who at some point in their lives each develop a lung disease. While Don's affliction results from a long history of addiction to tobacco, Naylor spontaneously develops lung tumours. Although there

might be reasons to make both cases distributively relevant, say in terms of necessity or even capabilities, under Dworkin's egalitarianism, Don would not have a claim since his action counts as an unsuccessful gamble, which, *ex hypothesi*, is excluded from the distributive inquiry.⁹⁷

- 60 Equivalently, contract law plays the egalitarian role of transforming a brute luck state of affairs into an option luck one. To this end, the consent rule from the institutional transaction scenario (previously referred to as R3), equates to the Dworkinian insurance market as the analytic device that conveys a specific exercise of control from the relevant class of agents: its parties. In this interpretation, consent is the relevant institutional fact through which they enter a distributive landscape by providing the normative criterion that allows the identification of control. Following Dworkin's metaphor, whenever the agreement occurs, the parties are *gambling*, meaning that they are mutually committing in view of a particular state of affairs where it is reasonable to expect, first, that their counterparty will comply and second, that the circumstances surrounding the agreement will at least prevail to the full performance. The last assumption is crucial to the distributive endeavour because to be successfully conducted, the exertion of control expressed through consent requires the avoidance of contractual failures arising from contractual misfortunes that exceed what the parties have mutually committed.
- 61 It is now time for my functional characterization of contract law, particularly the claim that contract law contains a set of rules that counteract the unfortunate impacts of the collaborative endeavours that it governs. In my interpretation of the rule of consent, contract law is especially keen to the occurrence of unforeseen, exorbitant, non-controllable circumstances, since, together with introducing reasons to collaborate with others (e.g., to allocate known risks), it also protects its parties from whatever unforeseen or unavoidable circumstance may endanger such a cooperative—but justified in terms of individual rationality—endeavour.
- 62 This particular feature can be observed in both contract law functions. Indeed, the legal concept of responsibility demands that the parties to a contract bear, like any subject to other branches of private law, the consequences arising from *their* breach. This can be translated into the dogmatic statement 'a is responsible for $\neg\varphi$ ', where φ is whatever benefit a promised to b. In our functional description, it is the role of the stabilizing function to provide content to statements such 'a is *obligated* to b to φ '.⁹⁸ Moreover, whenever the neutralization function comes into play, the normative criterion implied in it allows us to explain why 'a is responsible for $\neg\varphi$ ' does not always follow from 'a is obligated to b to φ '.
- 63 A party is liable for breaching a contract only if additional conditions are met. This feature can be interpreted as a result of its characterization as a legal assessment of responsibility grounded in a normative criterion such as fault, or at least the absence of circumstances that would render compliance impossible. From a moral perspective, it might be asserted that contract law demands the parties employ their best efforts to perform, considering that the breach must arise from an action attributable to them. Translated into egalitarian terminology, the debtor must *deserve* to bear the unfavourable effects because the breach, both legally and morally, is considered her own. This assertion is clarified through the French distinction between *obligations de moyens* (obligations of means) and *obligations de résultat* (obligations of result) since, from a legal-conceptual standpoint, it shows that the sole breach does not necessarily

satisfy a normative criterion for ordering compensation, even when the latter, which is the most demanding version of contractual liability, dispenses with the requirements of fault to make the debtor liable.⁹⁹

- 64 My theoretical argument can be fully deployed at last. If by justification we mean the articulation of reasons for having contract law *as it is*, from a liberal standpoint, it can be rendered as a worthwhile institution by attending to its capacity to *facilitate* the cooperative pursuit of autonomously defined individual life plans, given its functions of stabilizing and neutralization. Through them, sovereignly agreed transactions between private parties are most likely to be successfully concluded by discouraging opportunistic behaviour and protecting contractual plans from threats arising from unexpected circumstances. This (in a way, quite orthodox) contention does not imply, in any way whatsoever, that contract law should be designed to guarantee individual success in terms of accomplishments at all costs. Not even luck-egalitarians would subscribe to such a demanding conclusion. Contracts, like any constituent institution of private law, place the notion of consequential responsibility, a construct whose purpose is to allocate losses according to a criterion such as negligence or risk, in the center of its normative commitments. These criteria are grounded on moral foundations that may be provided by the egalitarian principle: If contract law is justifiable, it is because it embodies, at least in part, the liberal value of making people liable for their own deeds. In my interpretation, this egalitarian ideal is embodied in the moral requirement of control implied in the rule of consent, which, in turn, serves as a conceptual device that provides a normative criterion with sufficient breadth to serve as a foundation for both contract law functions. Finally, it must be concluded that when it comes to the practical implications arising from the assumption of an egalitarian public morality foundation for contract law, controversies such as the distributive query posed by Kronman should be affirmatively answered.

5 Final remarks

- 65 Regarding the philosophical foundations of contractual obligations, theoretical discussions usually begin with an inquiry into the legitimacy of contract law as a tool for pursuing valuable social goals beyond the individual interests of the parties, which are, by logical implication, external to what classical jurists identify as their juridical will.
- 66 As presented in the second section of this paper, my interpretative account of contract law begins with a morally neutral reconstruction of its main features (i.e., voluntariness and coercivity) based on a functional explanation of its rules. Given the context of epistemic uncertainty that threatens human cooperative endeavours ('Will she comply?', 'Why would I?', and so on), I argue that while contract law plays the primary function of stabilizing voluntary agreements, it also has the complementary function of neutralizing misfortunes. Likewise, I argued that the latter function is fulfilled by the characteristic description of contracts as mechanisms that allow people to create private schemes of allocation of foreseen risks as well as by their capacity to provide a regulatory framework to cope with unforeseen future contingencies that might affect such arrangements, like those constitutive of an act of God and *force majeure* hypothesis.

- 67 In the fourth section, I presented an argument in favour of a moral basis for a distributive justification of contract law, assuming that luck plays a significant role in assessing moral and legal responsibility. By contrasting it with the Razian interpretations of contract law reconstructed in the third section, I tried to demonstrate that the egalitarian principle is a suitable philosophical contender to found the distributive aims for this institution, considering its accessory function tending to correct consequences that, from a moral perspective, can be referred to as arbitrary and, by implication, unable to determine people's well-being or resources shares legitimately.
- 68 It should be noted that, to count as a good theory, any theoretical proposal about contract law not only has to shed light on the reasons for the parties to be legally bound to perform φ , but also explain why on occasion the same set of rules tolerates $\neg\varphi$. While in my account, the explanatory task is carried out through the functional categories of stabilization and neutralization, the corresponding normative premise rests on the moral principles that found contractors' liability for their deeds. When we refer to contract law's sensitivity to misfortunes, we mean something more than how perfectly informed parties can use these rules to prevent negative contingencies. Neither the most diligent contractor nor the most ingenious lawyer can anticipate every contingency that may affect them in the future. Here, the value of the philosophical commitments of the egalitarian principle are revealed: those who, facing future eventualities, *choose* to take refuge in contract law are performing an action the effects of which can be considered as constitutive of an option luck scenario, in such a way that whatever lands outside the scope of their consent entitles them to a distributive claim. Nothing more, nothing less. In this sense, contracts as social institutions perform both functions of facilitating contracting and preventing contingencies. This obtains whether the parties have expressly considered them or because of the implied terms that already have contemplated a way to solve unknown contingencies.¹⁰⁰
- 69 Such an approach advantages traditional distributive accounts of contract law, normally described as the *external* fairness requirement.¹⁰¹ On the contrary, my distributive account flows from the same ideal that demands that parties keep their word. One or the other possibility is plausible since contract law rests on the egalitarian premise that people are liable for their own deeds, meaning that they must comply with the contract, respond for their breach, but are not responsible for breaches whose causes lie outside their control.
- 70 As a final remark, like any other theorization about legal phenomena, where new answers are provided even more new queries appear. First, following pluralistic or mixed recommendations, it can be observed that while the egalitarian principle is pertinent, no conceptual reason prevents other moral ideals from participating in the normative and interpretative tasks of theorizing contract law. For instance, it may seem that traditional theories based on notions such as will and autonomy are better candidates for providing a moral basis for contracts, specifically due to their adequacy under the transparency criteria Smith identified.¹⁰² While plausible, I believe my approach still does as good of a job as a theoretical approach to contracts in terms of its fitness to contract rules, since its particularity, similar to efficiency theories, is just to assume a different standpoint from which the legal practice is observed; the Hartian external point of view.¹⁰³

- 71 Second, the assumption of a perspective based on luck egalitarianism premises raises further and new theoretical questions regarding some of the most puzzling queries raised by moral and political philosophers. I am thinking about topics such as the validity of the ‘ability to do otherwise’ as a condition for moral responsibility, famously criticized by Frankfurt;¹⁰⁴ the contractual rendition of what Cohen calls the ‘currency’ of egalitarian justice, i.e., concerning *what* private law should equally render people;¹⁰⁵ and the solution to the luck-neutralizers’ dilemma posed by Hurley, which, succinctly put, refers to the failure that the advocates of egalitarian positions oriented towards the neutralization of bad luck incur when it comes to providing a fair distribution principle.¹⁰⁶
- 72 Nevertheless, the complexity of such queries should not discourage distributive contract law theorists. Instead, they represent a challenging set of theoretical and empirical queries that will hopefully open a fertile field of concerns on which private law philosophers may reflect.

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NOTES

1. For instance, consider Smith's rejection of the strong version of the morality criterion applied to contract law interpretative queries (Smith 2004: 17-18), and Lucy's depiction of mixed

accounts of private law (Lucy 2007: 376-418). See also, Kreitner's (2012), Dagan's (2013), and Klass's (2020: 56) claims in favour of pluralistic accounts of contract law.

2. Coleman 1992: 9.

3. It should be noted that in this legal tradition, promissory theorists face a profound disagreement with accounts of contracts as legally binding *agreements*. Burrows 2016: 44.

4. Alessandri 2009: 10.

5. Kronman 1980; Atiyah 1990: 37; Jiménez 2017; Bagchi 2008, 2014; Papayannis 2016: 337.

6. Craswell 1991; Kaplow & Shavell 2002; Bix and Parisi 2024.

7. Ackerman 1971; Kennedy 1982; Fleming 2014; Williams 2019; Papayannis 2020; Davis & Pargendler 2022.

8. Raz 1986: 155; Kimel 2003: 149.

9. Kimel 2003: 134.

10. Sánchez (2023: 112), whose argument follows from Shiffrin's (1997) contention about the divergence between contracts and promises not just as a moral stand, but also as a metaphysical one.

11. Buckley 2005: 4.

12. Searle 1995: 27.

13. Searle 1995: 28.

14. Fried 2015: 17.

15. Following the civilian tradition notion of *obligatio* or obligation, by *in personam* right, I am referring to the creditor's correlative right to the debtor's duty to perform. Zimmermann 1996: 1.

16. Alessandri 2009: 6.

17. Barnett 2012: 647. It must be noted that Barnett's use of the word "consent" should not be confused with the doctrinal concept of consent shared in the Civil Law tradition. While Barnett characterizes it as a principle with implications for the moral justification of contracts (Barnett 1986), the legal term "consent" refers to the arguably most salient condition of the validity of contracts, which resembles the Hartian notion of power-conferring rules (Hart 1994: 41).

18. Barnett 2012: 658.

19. Zimmermann 1996: 10-11.

20. As Gaius posed in G. Inst. 3.88, '*omni enim obligatio uel ex contractu nascitu uel ex delicto*' [every obligation arises either from contract or from delict]. I owe the translation de Zulueta (1958: 179).

21. Guzmán 2012: 702.

22. Zimmermann 1996: 1-4.

23. Buckland & McNair 2008: 193-1944; Gordley 1992: 213.

24. Gordley 2006: 287-288.

25. Barnett 2012: 655.

26. Regarding this structural feature of private law, see Weinrib (1995: 8-14; 114-44).

27. Papayannis 2013.

28. I owe my comprehension of the idea of moral uncertainty to Michael J. Zimmerman (2008).

29. Coleman 1992: 106.

30. Sánchez 2023: 135.

31. Posner 2014: 3.

32. Sánchez 2023: 122.

33. Peterson 2009: 237.

34. Coleman 1992: 118.

35. Sánchez 2023: 128.

36. Sánchez 2023: 135.

37. Sánchez 2023: 127.

38. Zimmermann 1996: 4-6.

39. Zimmermann 1996: 688.

40. Buckland and McNair 2008: 243.
41. Burrows 2016: 164.
42. This is explained by a controversial interpretation of the Roman doctrines *res permit domino* ('the property is lost to its owner') and *res permit creditor* ('the property is lost to its creditor'), as taken by the Chilean codifier Andrés Bello. Alessandri 2011: 640.
43. *Tito v Wadel* (No. 2) [1977] Ch. 106, 326; *Patel v Ali* [1984] Ch. 238. For a doctrinal analysis of English common law, see Treitel 2008: 1717.
44. *Hadley v Baxendale* [1854] 9 Ex 341.
45. Berlin 2002: 178.
46. Raz 1986: 374.
47. Dagan 2013: 33, Klass 2012: 56. For a systematization, see Kreitner 2012.
48. Smith 2004: 139; Raz 1986: 369.
49. Raz 1986: 125.
50. Raz 1986: 369.
51. Raz 1986: 154.
52. Raz 1986: 111; Kimel 2003: 121.
53. As suggested by Smith's depiction of autonomy promotion theories of contract (Smith 2004: 139) and by Kimel's concept of personal detachment as an intrinsic function of contract law (Kimel 2003: 134).
54. Fried 2015: 16.
55. Kronman 1980: 472.
56. I take this description of Kimel's position from Smith (2004: 137).
57. Smith 2004: 134.
58. For an overview, see Lucy 2007: 343-375; Bagchi 2008; Bix & Parisi 2024.
59. Kronman 1980: 472.
60. Kant 1991: 63.
61. Benson 2010: 747; 2019: 367.
62. Consumer Rights Act 2015 ss 11-12; Consumer Contracts (Information, Cancellation and Additional Charges) Regulations 2013, pt 2.
63. The Food Information Regulations 2014.
64. Consumer Credit Act 1974, s 55; Financial Services and Markets Act 2000, s 80.
65. In *Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board* [2015] SC 11 [2015] 1 AC 1430, it was ruled that doctors have a duty to take reasonable care to ensure that their patients are aware of the material risks of injury inherent in the particular medical treatment.
66. The Human Medicines Regulations 2012, pt 13, ss 257 to 260.
67. Kimel 2003: 127-128.
68. Restatement of Contracts (Second) at §208 and the Uniform Commercial Code at § 2-302.
69. For a compilation of different rulings applying the doctrine, see Shiffrin (2000: 205).
70. Consumer Protection from Unfair Trading Regulations 2008, pt 2.
71. Raz 1986: 371.
72. Raz 1986: 370-373.
73. Williams 2002: 22.
74. Nagel 1979: 26.
75. Nagel 1979: 25.
76. Nelkin 2021: 3.
77. For egalitarianism, I understand a group of theories of political philosophy that reflect on the role of luck in allocating welfare or resources. Equality of opportunities, according to Kymlicka, asserts that people's fate should depend not on their circumstances but on their own choices. Kymlicka 2002: 58.
78. Rawls 1971: 15.

79. Rawls 1971: 62, 72, 102; 1982: 169-173.
80. Weinrib 1995.
81. Olsaretti 2009: 168.
82. Rawls 1971: 3-7; 1977: 164.
83. Hevia suggests, based on Aristotle's concept of justice as an ethical virtue, that this ideal of justice is appropriate for philosophically grounding contract law since it refers to a notion of justice "as justice in interpersonal relations" (Hevia 2023: 3).
84. In the classical view, distributive justice governs the relations between the community and its citizens—or between the whole and its parts—governing the centralized allocation of resources in 'geometrical' terms, according to a *public* criterion based on the notion of merit (Aristotle 1998: 245).
85. I owe this characterization to Gerald A. Cohen (1997: 3).
86. Rawls 1971: 3; 1977: 159.
87. Rawls 1971: 7.
88. Rawls 1971: 3; 1977: 159.
89. Rawls 2001: 53.
90. Rawls 1977: 164.
91. Cohen 1997: 11.
92. Rawls 1977: 160.
93. Sánchez 2022; Kordana & Tabachnick 2005: 598.
94. Sánchez 2022.
95. Dworkin 1981: 283.
96. Dworkin 1981: 286.
97. Dworkin 1981: 293.
98. See Barros 2006.
99. Demogue 1925: 536-544.
100. Coleman 1992: 173.
101. Bix & Parisi 2024.
102. Smith 2004: 24.
103. As in Hart 1994: 89.
104. Frankfurt 1998: 1-10.
105. Cohen 1989: 908.
106. Hurley 2003: 156.

ABSTRACTS

In contemporary scholarship, most proposals that refer to the moral foundations of contract law can be categorized under one of two broad conceptual categories: deontological (such as will, autonomy-based, and transference theories) and consequentialist (such as those rooted in efficiency and distributive justice considerations) theories. However, these conceptions are insufficient for adequately explaining and justifying contract rules because they either fail to grasp relevant features of the practice of contemporary voluntary transactions or they lose sight of the core content of this area of law. This paper aims to provide theoretical insights to mend

such shortcomings by redirecting the theorization of contracts towards an egalitarian liberal account of its social functions.

Razdelitveni temelji pogodbenega prava. Dandanes je večino predlogov, ki se nanašajo na moralne temelje pogodbenega prava, mogoče uvrstiti v eno od dveh širokih pojmovnih kategorij: deontološko (kamor sodijo teorije volje, avtonomije in prenosa) ter konsekencialistično (ki zajema teorije, utemeljene na učinkovitosti in vidikih razdelitvene pravičnosti). Vendar ta pojmovanja ne zagotavljajo ustrezne razlage in utemeljitve pogodbenopravnih pravil, saj bodisi ne zajamejo pomembnih značilnosti prakse sodobnih prostovoljnih transakcij bodisi spregledajo osrednjo vsebino tega pravnega področja. Namen razprave je odpraviti omenjeno pomankljivost s preusmeritvijo teoretskega razmisleka o pogodbenem pravu k egalitarno-liberalnemu pojmovanju družbenih funkcij pogodbe.

INDEX

Keywords: contract law theory, functional analysis, significant autonomy, egalitarianism

motsclessl teorija pogodbenega prava, funkcionalna analiza, avtonomija, egalitarizem

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